

Case Report of Gout Tophi: A Painful Step

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ABSTRACT

Gout tophi are characterized by an abnormal metabolism of uric acid, which leads to an undesirable accumulation of monosodium urate crystals that can be deposited in various body locations. We present a case of gout tophi in the heel of a 33-year-old male patient. Histopathological examination revealed pink amorphous deposits in the dermis, which validated the diagnosis of gout tophi. Tophi can be resolved and recurrence can be prevented through urate-lowering therapy.

Keywords: Gout tophi; Metabolism; Histopathological

INTRODUCTION

Gout tophi are common symptoms of gout and have significant clinical implications. Tophi are soft tissue urate deposits that occur in a variety of body locations. They are commonly observed in patients with chronic gout and are associated with more severe diseases and complications^[1]. The estimated prevalence of gout tophi in the general population of the United States is 1.2%^[2]. Tophi can result in joint deformity, erosion, and inflammation, which can contribute to chronic arthropathy and synovitis^[3]. Moreover, tophi can be associated with complications such as spinal cord compression and renal damage^[4,5]. We present a case of gout tophi in the heel of a 33-year-old male patient.

CASE PRESENTATION

We report a 33-year-old non-alcoholic male patient with a 6-year history of gout, who was referred to our dermatological outpatient unit with the presentation of a whitish skin lesion on the left heel presented for 1 year. The lesion size increased gradually and started to be painful and bleed one month ago, affecting his daily life

activities. The patient didn't report any similar lesions elsewhere in the body currently or previously. He is on allopurinol however not complaint. On the physical examination, his vital signs were stable. The lesion was exophytic with white exudate on the left heel, measuring 3.5 x 2.5 cm (Figure 1). On further workup, basic labs were unremarkable including normal creatinine level, except the uric acid level of 7.9 milligrams per deciliter (mg/dL). A biopsy was taken for histopathological examinations which revealed deposits of pale pink material in the dermis with foreign body reaction around deposits (Figure 2), confirming the diagnosis of gout. The patient was treated with colchicine 1 mg daily and high-dose glucocorticoids, which showed significant improvement.

Figure 1: The lesion was exophytic with white exudate on the left heel, the blue marker is the site of punch biopsy.

Figure 2: The biopsy specimen from the left heel shows deposits of pale pink material in the dermis with foreign body reaction around deposits.

DISCUSSION

Numerous clinical implications are associated with the presence of tophi in patients with gout. Tophi are frequently associated with a greater disease burden, including more frequent gout attacks, greater activity impairment, and decreased quality of life^[3]. In addition, the presence of tophi is associated with a higher risk of mortality, especially from cardiovascular causes^[6]. Tophi can also have negative effects on renal function, with studies demonstrating a precipitous decline in renal function among gout patients having tophi^[7]. The early onset of subcutaneous tophi in patients with gout has also been linked to decreased creatinine clearance^[8].

The pathophysiology of tophi consists of multiple phases. Initially, there is hyperuricemia without evidence of monosodium urate crystal deposition or gout. This is followed by crystal deposition in the absence of gout symptoms, which may progress to crystal deposition during acute gout attacks. The presence of tophi, chronic gouty arthritis, and radiographic erosions characterize advanced gout. The gold standard method for the diagnosis of gout tophi is skin biopsy and the presence of chalk-like material on the open skin and around joints^[9], as seen in our patient. Tophi typically develop more than ten years after the onset of gout and are regarded as a late manifestation of the disease^[10].

Gout tophi are typically found in and around joints, but they can also occur in subcutaneous tissues, tendons, and even the vocal cords^[11]. In addition, gout tophi have been found in the septal cartilage and nasal tip [12]. They are visible in the human body as yellowish-white nodules of varying diameters with thin surfaces. Upon rupture, a white substance may be expelled, typically over an extended period. Rarely, secondary infections are observed

in tophi^[12]. Tophi at atypical sites may be misdiagnosed, and in many cases, they are discovered accidentally by pathology, surgery, or imaging^[13].

Tophi can be treated with urate-lowering medications such as allopurinol and pegloticase. Tophi can be resolved and recurrence is prevented through urate-lowering therapy^[14]. Owing to the efficacy of medical treatment, surgical intervention is rarely required for gouty tophi. Surgical intervention is necessary if the tophi agonize and exhibit imminent skin necrosis, infection, ulceration, tendon impairment, mechanical impairment, nerve compression, and joint degeneration^[15].

CONCLUSION

Gout tophi are soft tissue urate deposits that can occur in numerous locations throughout the body. Tophi are frequently associated with a greater disease burden, including more frequent gout attacks, greater activity impairment, and decreased quality of life. The diagnostic gold standard for gout tophi is a skin biopsy and the presence of chalk-like material on the affected location. Tophi can be eliminated and their recurrence prevented through urate-lowering therapy.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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